

THE APPLICATION OF PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE MODELLING TECHNIQUES TO THE STUDY OF DELAMINATION EFFECTS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The analysis and prediction of the development of damage in composite materials, and its influence on their final failure, represent an important area of study. The application of the techniques of progressive damage modelling, using finite element analysis, has proved to be a valuable methodology for investigating the propagation of various types of damage.

The present work focuses on applying these techniques to the study of delamination effects in carbon fibre reinforced composite materials. In particular, modelling work has been carried out to investigate the development of free-edge delamination of specimens loaded in tension, using the ABAQUS finite element analysis code. Predictions of the growth of delamination are seen to be in good agreement with published data.

Keywords: Composites, Damage, Delamination, Failure, Modelling.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the principal attractions of composite materials is their ability to accommodate significant sub-critical damage prior to final failure. The analysis and prediction of the development of various types of damage, therefore represent a most important area of study as regards the structural performance of composite components. The application of the techniques of progressive damage modelling, using finite element analysis, has demonstrable value as a future structural design and assessment tool for routine use by materials engineers [1 - 4].

2. SPECIMEN GEOMETRY

The present work has focused on applying progressive damage modelling techniques to the study of free edge delamination effects in carbon fibre reinforced epoxy based composites. The modelling work has been carried out using the ABAQUS finite element analysis code [5] using techniques developed at SRD [6]. The specimen lay-up considered during the investigation, was based on that used by Schellekens and de Borst [7], having a [+25 / -25 / 90]_s lay-up. One particular area of interest was the resin-rich layer, found between the laminates, these were modelled as separate layers, assuming mechanical properties appropriate for the resin system. The importance of utilising suitable material failure criteria and material property degradation rules has also been considered.

The analyses considered a three-dimensional model of a specimen having the dimensions shown in Figure 1. Considerations of symmetry dictated that one-eighth of the specimen would adequately represent the behaviour, and the finite element model adopted is shown in Figure 2. The model consisted of 1662, 8 node plane strain brick elements, to model the three plies and three resin-rich interface layers, with an increased area of refinement at the central section of the specimen.

A cross sectional representation of the specimen with the interfacial, resin-rich layers being represented, is shown in Figure 3.

3. PERFORMANCE OF THE MODEL

Incrementally increasing strains were applied to the model and failure criteria based on the following formulation were applied:

$$\sqrt{(S_{11}/S_{UTS})^2 + (S_{22}/S_{UTS})^2 + (S_{33}/S_{UTS})^2 + (S_{12}/S_{SS})^2 + (S_{13}/S_{SS})^2 + (S_{23}/S_{SS})^2} \geq 1 \equiv \text{leads to damage of the element being considered} \quad (1)$$

where: S_{nn} = stress in the directions indicated in Figs. 1 and 2 :
 $n = 1, 2 \text{ or } 3$

S_{UTS} and S_{SS} = ultimate tensile and shear failure stresses in the appropriate directions

Suitable material property degradation rules were applied to the damaged elements and the effect on the predicted evolution of damage was investigated.

4. RESULTS

The damage propagation predicted by the model, for the central resin-rich interfacial layer, is shown as a function of applied strain in Figure 4. The failure is essentially Mode I, being driven by the S_{33} component of stress. The area of delamination is seen to grow inwards from the edge of the specimen, and some internal delamination is seen prior to total failure of the layer.

The corresponding evolution of damage in the 90° ply is shown in Figure 5. This is essentially transverse ply cracking, driven by the S_{11} component of stress.

The results obtained may be compared with those presented in [7], in particular with reference to the growth of free edge delamination; see Figure 6. Reasonable agreement is seen.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The present work has shown that delamination development and propagation in multi-ply composite materials may be adequately represented using finite element analysis methods and the techniques of progressive damage modelling. The importance of modelling the resin-rich interfacial layer has been demonstrated.

In future work, it is proposed to examine a probabilistic approach to damage development in composite materials, in order to account for the effects of voids and localised property variability in the materials.

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Figure 1 Specimen Geometry

Figure 2 Finite Element Model Used for Delamination Study

Figure 3 Cross Section of Model Showing Resin-Rich Layers

Fig. 4 Propagation of Delamination Damage in the Central Resin-Rich Interfacial Layer

Fig. 5 Propagation of Transverse Ply Cracking in the 90° Ply

Figure 6 Delamination Length as a Function of Applied Strain